

Reactions of Methyltrimethoxysilane with Glycols. Part-I

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Reactions have been carried out between methyltrimethoxysilane and different glycols in benzene with silane-glycol molar ratio 1:1 and 2:3. The glycols tried were ethylene, propylene, hexylene, pinacol, hexamethylene and butane diol 1,4. The reactions in molar ratio 2:3 appeared to be slower and required the use of *p*-toluene sulphonic acid as a catalyst. The reaction provides a new route for the synthesis of heterocyclic organosilicon compounds containing the silicon atom in the ring.

IN 1944, Kipping and Abrams¹ carried out reactions between dimethyldichlorosilane and ethylene glycol but failed to prepare ethylene-dioxy-dimethylsilane,

as a five-membered ring. Later Krieble and Burkhard² reported that the product formed by reacting the above two reactants was a dimer and a ten-membered ring was assigned to it.

Waterman and Breederveld³ studied the reaction between tetrachlorosilane and ethylene glycol, the initial product so formed was assigned a formula $(\text{CH}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{SiCl}_2)_2$. This compound on heating split off tetrachlorosilane and gave a tacky mass.

In view of the very reactive nature of tetrachlorosilane and thereby failing to isolate a pure product, other workers^{1,2,4} carried out reactions with alkyltrichloro⁴ and dialkyldichlorosilanes^{1,2} and glycols, but in these cases also complications were reported to have occurred.

Further the work on glycolysis has been extended by Mehrotra and Narain⁵, who prepared cyclic compounds containing silicon atom in the ring by treating tetraalkoxy and trialkoxysilane with various glycols.

It, therefore, appears that while much work has been done with tetrachloro, alkyltrichloro, dialkyldichloro, trialkoxy or tetraalkoxysilane and various glycols, comparatively little work appears to have been done with alkyltrialkoxo or alkyltrialkoxysilane and different glycols. It was thought worthwhile to carry out reactions with alkyltrialkoxysilane and various glycols. For this purpose methyltrimethoxysilane was chosen firstly because of the less steric hindrance in its molecule due to the presence of less bulky groups and secondly because of the activating influence of the methyl group bonded to the silicon atom.

The reactions of methyltrimethoxysilane and ethylene, propylene, hexylene, pinacol, hexamethylene and butane diol 1,4 were carried out in benzene with silane-glycol molar ratio 1 : 1 and 2 : 3.

Representing the glycol by the general formula

the reactions can be represented by the following equations :

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The progress of the reaction was studied by carefully fractionating the alcohol formed azeotropically with benzene and estimating it periodically.

Results and Discussion

While reactions were fairly facile in molar ratio 1 : 1, they appeared to be slow in silane-glycol molar ratio 2 : 3 and *p*-toluene sulphonic acid was added as a catalyst to push the reaction to completion. Excess solvent was removed first by distillation and last traces were finally removed under vacuum. Where the compounds formed were non-distillable solids, they were purified by washing with dry diethylether. In cases where they were liquids, the pure product was obtained by distillation under reduced pressure.

The silicon derivatives of ethylene, propylene, hexamethylene and butane diol 1, 4 in molar ratio 1 : 1 and 2 : 3 were solids insoluble in benzene, chloroform, carbontetrachloride and *n*-hexane. These derivatives did not melt and appeared to char on heating. Only pinacol and hexylene glycol gave colourless liquids distillable under reduced pressure which was soluble in above solvents.

The results obtained from the glycolysis of methyltrimethoxysilane show that the reactions are facile due to the presence of less bulky methoxy groups and also due to the activating influence of the methyl group attached to the silicon atom. These results are also corroborated by the earlier work of Mehrotra and Narain⁵ who have studied the reactions of triethoxysilane and glycols in molar ratio 1 : 1 and 2 : 3. In these cases also the reaction in molar ratio 1 : 1 appeared to be comparatively faster than that where the silane-glycol molar ratio was 2 : 3. Similar reactions by the same workers between tetramethoxysilane and glycols (loc.cit.) led to the conclusion that in this series also the reactions were faster in molar ratio 1 : 1 than in silane-glycol molar ratio 1 : 2.

Further, the glycols with hydroxyl groups in adjacent positions were much reactive than those in which they are far apart.

In some of the cases the reactions appear to be catalysed by *p*-toluenesulphonic acid.

The above method provides a convenient route for almost quantitative synthesis of heterocyclic organosilicon compounds containing silicon atom in the ring.

Experimental

General

All the reactions and manipulations were performed in moisture free atmosphere.

Benzene, glycols, diethylether, and methyltrimethoxy silane were purified by standard procedures.

Methanol was estimated in the azeotrope by the method given in the literature⁶.

I.R. and N.M.R. spectra were recorded neat at the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow (U.P.). The results were interpreted by comparing the values with those reported in standard books⁷⁻¹⁰.

Reactions between methyltrimethoxysilane and ethylene glycol in molar ratio 1 : 1

A homogeneous mixture of methyltrimethoxysilane (2.05 g), ethylene glycol (0.94 g) and benzene (24.5 g) was refluxed for 2 hours. Methanol (0.94 g.) formed as a product was azeotropically fractionated (2 moles require 0.96 g). The excess solvent was removed first over the column and then in vacuum at 60°/5mm. for 2 hours. The white crystalline solid (1.99 g; 98.5%) of methylmethoxyglycoxy silane was finally washed with few cc (~10 cc) of diethylether and dried at 60°/5mm. for 2 hours. (Found: Si, 20.89, SiC₄H₁₀O₈ requires Si, 20.91%).

The compound was insoluble in benzene and *n*-hexane and decomposed without melting at high temperatures.

Replacement of methoxy by *n*-butoxy in the above compound

A mixture of compound (0.89 g), *n*-butanol (0.49 g), and benzene (26.5 g) after refluxing for 2 hours liberated methanol (0.19 g) which was azeotropically fractionated (one mole requires 0.21 g). The reaction mixture after drying gave yellowish white solid (1.10 g; 94.8%). (Found: Si, 15.88; SiC₃H₇O₂.OC₄H₉ requires Si, 15.92%). It decomposed without melting at high temperature.

Reaction between methyltrimethoxysilane and ethylene glycol in molar ratio 2 : 3

Refluxed the mixture containing ethylene glycol (1.38 g), methyltrimethoxysilane (2.02 g), and benzene (25.5 g) for 3 hours. Methanol (0.84 g) was fractionated azeotropically (6 moles require 1.42 g). A crystal of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid was added followed by benzene (20.0 g) and the contents were refluxed for 8 hours. Methanol (0.50 g) was again fractionated. A white crystalline solid (1.82 g; 92.3%) was obtained when freed from solvent. (Found: Si, 21.03; Si₂C₈H₁₈O₆ requires Si, 21.07%). It decomposed without melting.

Methods of preparation being the same for all the reactions, a summary is given in tables 1, 2 and 3. Some of the compounds were also characterised by their spectral studies (I.R. and N.M.R.).

TABLE 1. REACTIONS BETWEEN METHYLTRIMETHOXYSILANE AND GLYCOLS IN MOLAR RATIO 1:1

Reactants	Amount (g)	Observation during mixing	Ref-lux period (hr)	Methanol in azeotrope (Found)	Conditions of drying	Nature of product (after removal of benzene)	Distillation	Product and yield (%)	Si (%) Found	Si (%) Calc.	
CH ₃ .Si(OCH ₃) ₃ + ethylene glycol	2.05	Colourless homogeneous solution	2	0.94	0.96	60°C/5mm 2 hrs.	White solid	Non-distillable solid	Si ₁ C ₈ H ₁₀ O ₃ [*] 98.5	20.89	20.91
CH ₃ .Si(OCH ₃) ₃ + propylene glycol	1.06	Colourless homogeneous solution	2	0.47	0.49	60°C/4mm 2 hrs.	White solid	Non-distillable solid	Si ₁ C ₈ H ₁₂ O ₃ [*] 99.09	18.91	18.93
CH ₃ .Si(OCH ₃) ₃ + butane diol 1,4	1.54	Colourless homogeneous solution	4	0.71	0.72	50°C/2mm 30 mins	White solid	Non-distillable solid	Si ₁ C ₈ H ₁₄ O ₃ [*] 98.3	17.28	17.29
CH ₃ .Si(OCH ₃) ₃ + Pinacol	1.30	Colourless homogeneous solution	6½	0.53	0.61	65°C/2.5mm 1 hr.	Light Yellow liquid	Colourless liquid at 137°C/0.9mm/ 200°C.Soluble in benzene	Si ₁ C ₈ H ₁₈ O ₃ [*] 84.5	14.70	14.74
CH ₃ .Si(OCH ₃) ₃ + hexylene glycol	1.37	Colourless homogeneous solution	7	0.63	0.64	60°C/5mm 2 hrs.	Colourless liquid	Colourless liquid at 135-36°C/0.6mm/ 200°C.Soluble in benzene	Si ₁ C ₈ H ₁₈ O ₃ [*] 78.9	14.71	14.74
CH ₃ .Si(OCH ₃) ₃ + hexamethylene glycol	1.02	Colourless homogeneous solution	7½	0.44	0.47	65°C/4mm 2 hrs.	White solid	Non-distillable solid	Si ₁ C ₈ H ₁₈ O ₃ [*] 91.45	14.80	14.74

* Compound did not melt in its melting point determination when heated in a sealed capillary tube and was insoluble in benzene and *n*-hexane.

TABLE 2. REPLACEMENT OF METHOXY BY *n*-BUTOXY IN THE PRODUCT OF MOLAR RATIO 1:1

Reactants	Amount (g)	Ref-lux period (hr)	Methanol in azeotrope (Found)	Conditions of drying	Nature of product (after removal of benzene)	Distillation	Product and yield (%)	Si (%) Found	Si (%) Calc.	
Product of ethylene glycol + butanol ⁿ	0.89	2	0.19	0.21	60°C/4mm 1 hr.	Yellowish white solid	Non-distillable solid	Si ₁ C ₈ H ₇ O ₃ .OC ₄ H ₉ ^{n*} 94.8	15.88	15.92
Product of propylene glycol + butanol ⁿ	0.88	4	0.13	0.19	62°C/4-5mm 1 hr.	Light Yellow solid	Non-distillable solid	Si ₁ C ₈ H ₉ O ₃ .OC ₄ H ₉ ^{n*} 75.4	14.70	14.74
Product of butane diol 1,4 + butanol ⁿ	0.65	4	0.10	0.12	58°C/3mm 2 hrs.	White solid	Non-distillable solid	Si ₁ C ₈ H ₁₁ O ₃ .OC ₄ H ₉ ^{n*} 95.5	13.71	13.73
Product of hexamethylene glycol + butanol ⁿ	0.79	4	0.12	0.13	60°C/4-5mm 2 hrs.	White solid	Non-distillable solid	Si ₁ C ₇ H ₁₅ O ₃ .OC ₄ H ₉ ^{n*} 83.3	12.02	12.07

* Compounds were insoluble in benzene and in attempted determination of melting point in a sealed capillary, they did not appear to melt.

TABLE 3. REACTIONS BETWEEN METHYLTRIMETHOXYSLANE AND GLYCOLS IN MOLAR RATIO 2:3

Reactants	Amount (g)	Observation during mixing	Ref. lux period (hr)	Methanol in azeotrope (g) Found Calc.	Conditions of drying	Nature of Product (after removal of benzene)	Distillation	Product and yield (%)	Si (%) Found Calc.
CH ₃ Si(OCH ₃) ₃	2.02	Clear homogeneous solution	8	1.34 1.42	62°C/4mm 1 hr.	White solid	Non-distillable solid	Si ₂ C ₈ H ₁₈ O ₆ 92.3	21.03 21.07
+ ethylene glycol	1.38								
CH ₃ Si(OCH ₃) ₃	1.24	Colourless homogeneous solution	8	0.84 0.87	65°C/3mm 2 hrs.	White solid	Non-distillable solid	Si ₂ C ₁₁ H ₂₄ O ₆ 98.57	18.13 18.19
+ propylene glycol	1.04								
CH ₃ Si(OCH ₃) ₃	1.11	Colourless homogeneous solution	9	0.72 0.78	60°C/3mm 30 mints	White solid	Non-distillable solid	Si ₂ C ₁₄ H ₃₀ O ₆ 97.8	15.99 16.01
+ butane diol	1.4								
CH ₃ Si(OCH ₃) ₃	2.96	Clear homogeneous solution	11	2.01 2.08	60°C/5mm	Yellowish liquid	Colourless oily liquid	Si ₂ C ₁₀ H ₂₂ O ₆	Ist 12.82 2nd 12.91
+ Pinacol	3.85								
CH ₃ Si(OCH ₃) ₃	1.17	Colourless homogeneous solution	10	0.80 0.82	75°C/4mm 1 hr.	Colourless liquid	Colourless oily liquid	Si ₂ C ₂₀ H ₄₂ O ₆ 96.2	12.93 12.91
+ hexylene glycol	1.52								
CH ₃ Si(OCH ₃) ₃	1.05	Colourless homogeneous solution	13	0.73 0.74	65°C/4mm 2 hrs.	White solid	Non-distillable solid	Si ₂ C ₂₀ H ₄₂ O ₆ 95.8	12.90 12.91
+ hexamethylene glycol	1.36								
I. R. Spectra :— Si ₂ C ₈ H ₁₈ O ₆			Band (cm ⁻¹)				Assignment		
			1070-1030 (broad)				Si—O—C cyclic		
			1260				Si—CH ₃		
			1365				—C(CH ₃) ₂ (gem, dimethyl)		
			1180				—OCH ₃		
N. M. R. Spectra :— Si ₂ C ₈ H ₁₈ O ₆			τ values		no. of protons		Assignment		
			10.01		3		Si—CH ₃		
			8.85		9		CH ₂ —C		
			6.6		3		—OCH ₃		
			5.85		2		CH ₂ —C		
			5.45		1		CH—O		
Si ₂ C ₂₀ H ₄₂ O ₆			τ values		no. of protons		Assignment		
			10.01		6		Si—CH ₃		
			8.85		27		CH ₂ —C		
			5.95		6		CH ₂ —C		
			5.4		3		CH—O		

*Compounds were white crystalline solid, insoluble in benzene and *n*-hexane and in melting point determination they decomposed when heated in a sealed capillary tube.

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